

Sampling bag

Sample collections were carried out using a static-shielding polyethylene bag containing an aluminized polyester middle layer (30" width x 46" height, McMASTER-CARR, 4663T9). At the top of the plastic bag, five orifices were positioned for: (1) vacuum outlet for cleaning; (2) vacuum line for sampling; (3) RH sensor (Honeywell, HIH-5030); (4) TSI-3330 optical particle sizer; and (5) ultra-clean anhydrous air inlet (**Scheme 1**). The top of the bag was reinforced with a horizontal aluminum sheet (24" x 6" x 3/8") placed inside the bag, which had the above-mentioned ports precisely drilled through. The edges and corners of the aluminum sheet were rounded, and it was wrapped in static-shielding film to prevent damaging the bag. The bag was suspended inside a clean-air enclosure by hooks that were anchored in the aluminum sheet. A valve at the front face of the bag served as an exhalation port.

Scheme 1. Experimental setup for bioaerosol generation and collection

Sample collection

Prior to each sampling experiment, a 3-micron PTFE filter (TISCH Scientific, SF18183) was freshly washed with ethanol (10 mL, 30% MQ water) and attached to the sampling port of the bag. The bag was then filled with 80 L of ultra-clean dry air, while the volunteer spent a minimum of one minute breathing inside the clean room before performing snoring maneuvers. Using a plastic pipette, betaine solution (2 mL, 1 M) was applied to the back of the throat and tongue, targeting the areas that come into transient touching during snoring. Any excess solution was swallowed to cover regions inaccessible by pipetting. Subsequently, a series of 5 snoring maneuvers were executed. Throughout the snoring actions, air was inhaled from the clean enclosure and then exhaled into the collection bag. This entire procedure was repeated three times (resulting in a total of 15 snoring cycles), after which the humidity inside the bag reached 50-53%. This rise in humidity is equivalent to 27 L of exhaled air under the assumption that exhaled air is fully saturated at 37 °C. Upon the completion of the snoring maneuvers, a saliva sample was promptly gathered from the back of the throat and tongue using a long cotton swab (MediChoice, WOD1004) for quantification of betaine in saliva by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. Following a delay to allow precipitation of any spurious larger particles, air from the bag was drawn through the PTFE filter at a flow rate of 6 L/min for a duration of 14 minutes (totaling 84 L). During this sample collection, the particles inside the bag were characterized using a TSI-3330 optical particle sizer, drawing air from the bag at a rate of 1 L/min (total of 14 L). For particle size distributions, see **Table 1**. For the control experiment, snoring actions were replaced by breathing at the same rate and volume.

Quantification of betaine in saliva

The mass of saliva was determined gravimetrically before the swab was washed with D₂O (0.7 mL). The sample was then transferred to a 5-mm NMR tube for analysis. A standard 1-D PRESAT experiment available from the Bruker library was used to suppress the residual water resonance. The concentrations of betaine in saliva samples are shown in **Table 2**.

Sample processing and derivatization for liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS):

Betaine, a widely used food supplement, is a suitable chemical marker for oral fluids. Its nine chemically equivalent methyl protons yield a sharp singlet in the NMR spectrum, enabling sensitive NMR detection. Betaine's quantification through mass spectrometry (MS), however, is hampered due to its low pKa of 1.8, leading to a zwitterionic state with an overall neutral charge at pH levels compatible with most LC-MS instruments and suitable columns for its separation. To enhance its MS sensitivity, it was esterified to form a product with net positive charge using the reaction conditions outlined in **Scheme 2**.

Scheme 2. Conversion of zwitterionic betaine to its positively charged ester derivative for enhanced quantification.

After sample collection, the trapped contents were eluted from the filters into total recovery LC-MS vials (Waters, 186000384C) by ethanol (400 μ L, 30% MQ water) driven by a plastic syringe. Subsequently, the eluted solution was spiked with a betaine-*d*₁₁ solution (10 μ L, 10 μ M) followed by evaporation to dryness using a high-temperature setting on a speedvac (ThermoSavant, DNA110). After that, the residue was resuspended in ethanolic HCl (50 μ L, Sigma-Aldrich, 17934) and heated on a hot plate at 85 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 hour with the vial caps tightened (**Scheme 2**). After subsequent evaporation of all volatiles, the residue was resuspended in solvent A, comprised of 98% acetonitrile and 2% aqueous ammonium formate (200 mM, pH 3.0). A 5- μ L portion of this solution was loaded into an analytical HILIC-Z column (2.1 x 50 mm, 2.7 μ m, Agilent, 689775-924) that had been pre-equilibrated with solvent A at 15 $^{\circ}$ C. Elution was performed using an isocratic flow of the same solvent at a rate of 0.4 mL/min (Agilent, 1260 Infinity LC system). Quantification of the betaine ester (146.1 m/z) was achieved by comparing its peak area to that of the betaine-*d*₁₁ ester (157.2 m/z). Both chromatograms were obtained by the selective ion monitoring method using a single quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent, model 6130B) operating in positive ion mode with a fragmentor and capillary voltages of 120 and 1,500 volts, respectively. The electrospray nebulizer pressure was set to 35 psig and the drying gas flow and temperature were 12 L/min and 350 $^{\circ}$ C, respectively. The mass of betaine per total bag volume are listed in **Table 2** for each measurement.

Table 1. Number of particles per L of exhaled air measured detected by TSI-3330 OPS.

bin (micron)	breathing					snoring				
	# 1	# 2	# 3	# 4	# 5	# 1	# 2	# 3	# 4	# 5
0.30-0.37	756	1244	1180	1499	1419	3513	3704	2534	2691	4883
0.37-0.47	592	877	751	1124	1119	2788	2761	2149	2034	3172
0.47-0.58	484	811	622	916	929	2367	2231	1851	1683	2228
0.58-0.72	368	582	444	673	634	1446	1325	1205	1062	1277
0.72-0.90	199	337	247	375	374	744	734	669	568	653
0.90-1.12	265	471	340	521	553	1042	932	890	785	879
1.12-1.39	90	139	96	160	166	295	286	253	231	259
1.39-1.73	79	165	104	154	199	329	315	273	268	283
1.73-2.16	39	65	55	72	94	149	148	115	102	126
2.16-2.69	9	14	8	11	17	26	21	21	21	20
2.69-3.34	5	3	2	4	4	4	5	5	3	5
3.34-4.16	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
4.16-5.18	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
5.18-6.45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6.45-8.03	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8.03-10.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Betaine contents of PTFE filters and saliva quantified by LC-MS and NMR, respectively.

experiment	betaine in aerosols (ng) ^a	betaine in saliva (mM) ^b	aerosolized saliva (pL/L) ^c
breathing 1	0.03	289	0.04 ^d
breathing 2	0.06	291	0.08 ^d
breathing 3	0.05	134	0.15 ^d
breathing 4	0.05	211	0.10 ^d
breathing 5	0.06	231	0.10 ^d
snoring 1	9.77	150	26.7
snoring 2	11.12	84	53.4
snoring 3	5.46	143	15.4
snoring 4	6.71	114	23.7
snoring 5	10.17	101	40.6

^a Total mass of betaine collected from the PTFE filter. For breathing measurements these are upper limits, determined by the baseline in the mass spectrum.

^b Concentration of betaine in saliva after 3 times 5 breathing and snoring maneuvers, with each set of 5 preceded by application, gargling, and swallowing of 2 mL of a 1 M betaine solution.

^c Estimated quantity of oral fluid captured by the PTFE filter. pL aerosolized saliva per L of exhaled air.

^d Impurities present in the baseline of the MS may contribute to these values and reported values are upper limits for the true saliva contents